

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION - COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN CHEMISTRY

Matsalaeva Sayera Zaripbaevna.

Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry
and Biotechnology, Nukus Branch. Assistant teacher.

Elubaeva Raya Orazbay qizi

Student of Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, Animal
Husbandry and Biotechnology University, Nukus branch

ABSTRACT: *In the article, a special socio-cultural environment should be formed in pedagogical education conducted on the basis of information and communication technologies (ICT) in higher pedagogical educational institutions (qualification (level) "bachelor"), - the need to create an environment for the development of personality traits such as self-organization and self-management ability, intellectuality is shown.*

Key words: *ICT, pedagogical education, socio-cultural environment, intellectuality, ability.*

INTRODUCTION

At present, there is a rapidly developing global informatization process, therefore, in order to understand and study global hydro-ecological problems, both specialists who are trained in higher and secondary special educational institutions under the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources, as well as mathematical modeling . They, in turn, solve practical problems and tasks related to their specialties using hydrochemical information and data, electronic training manuals, find, collect, process, and store the necessary information and data for themselves. and should develop transfer skills.

In connection with the introduction of new information and communication tools into the educational process, the term computer educational technologies for students appeared. Today, this term reflects a holistic scientifically developed

methodology of using a system of tools, methods and educational methods. At the same time, the scientific-methodical concept that combines the above system with a single general didactic idea for use in the educational process in order to effectively solve the triad task (education, development and training of students) is the basis serves. "Computer technology" at school is one of the means of implementing pedagogical technologies used in each individual case.

Naturally, it is impossible to achieve the most effective results in teaching, developing and educating students, which can be done by using only one of any technology. A systematic, complex, customized approach to the application of all available pedagogical technologies, techniques and methods, adapted to a specific school, allows a specific teacher to achieve good results in the educational process

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It is also possible to use the interactive document "Set of Tasks" in training future chemist teachers and improving their intellectual ability. Pedagogical for use in the teaching-methodical process - to create new types of multimedia electronic textbooks and master-templates - using Microsoft Office, Microsoft's modern package programs, MS Word, Power Point, E-Publisher, Excel spreadsheet, it is also possible to use programs such as database (Access). Based on the above programs, teaching based on multimedia master templates, testing the acquired knowledge based on the rating system, is comprehensive and high level.

"General chemistry", "Inorganic chemistry", "Analytical chemistry", "Organic chemistry", "Physical and colloid chemistry", "Chemical technology", "Biochemistry" are integrated with ICT in higher educational institutions. teaching, in which it is possible to use the elements of ICT and pedagogical technologies in accordance with the requirements of the time.

ICT education is a complex process that cannot be completed by providing schools with computers, e-textbooks and Internet connections. ICT education should be considered more broadly, aimed at the implementation of the triple goal of

teaching, education and development, which provides the theory, methodology and practice of improving the educational process through the introduction of ICT tools, their development and use, and the teacher himself must be ready for this.

The main directions of ICT education are reflected in the following:

- 1) formation of an educational environment based on "cloud" technologies;
- 2) modernization of the technical infrastructure of informatization of the educational system to do;
- 3) development of electronic educational resources of the educational system;
- 4) ensuring the mutual exchange of information in the network of the participants of the educational process;
- 5) expansion of distance learning in education;
- 6) development of personnel in the field of ICT education;
- 7) full provision of education management system with ICT.

In our opinion, consideration of the possibilities of teaching chemistry has not been given sufficient attention in contemporary methodological literature. Thus, I.A. Kutney considered the problem of developing self-discipline skills in teaching general chemistry; G.I. Egorova proposed an author's methodology for organizing the educational process for graduates, taking into account the requirements of educational organizations. N.I. Komarova recommends the wide use of project activities to assess the level of formation of chemical competence, which determines the quality of the future specialist's personality, including chemical literacy, experience in applying chemical knowledge in solving production problems. The use of IT technologies, the pursuit of self-development and self-education. However, in our opinion, the theoretical-methodical and didactic foundations of the implementation of the requirements of the contextual-competence approach in the educational process are not sufficiently developed in the literature.

In the future, the following are the main directions of informing the educational institution where the current chemist-student works:

- Equipping the material base of the school in general and the school chemistry room in particular with ICT tools (computer equipment and software).
- creation of electronic educational resources (information and information, monitoring, diagnostics, interactive) in order to use them in the process of teaching chemistry and to monitor its results.
- development of educational and methodological support, including the use of new information media and technologies together with traditional forms, methods and tools of chemistry education.
- training of future chemistry teachers and improving the skills of practicing teachers in the use of new ICTs in chemistry teaching.

Currently, general secondary educational institutions in our Republic have software that supports the teaching of academic subjects using computer technologies. In educational institutions, automation of management activities, social and psychological services have been established, libraries are provided with software for automation of activities.

Internet access is established in general secondary educational institutions. It allows us to conclude that the majority of educational institutions are sufficiently equipped with a material base, which allows the implementation of the ideas of educational informatization in school practice.

Forms, methods and means of using ICT in the educational process are actively developing in the modern chemistry teaching methodology. At the same time, in order to improve the quality of school chemistry education in general, it is to search for their combination with traditional forms, methods and tools of chemistry teaching.

Currently, the problem of teaching future chemistry teachers to use a virtual chemical experiment is being discussed. T.P. Tretyakova, Yu.B. Ikrennikova, I.V. In Larner's dissertation work, an attempt was made to reveal the problem of using

virtual experiments in teaching, and this in itself motivated the development of this direction.

When studying the electronic structure of inorganic and organic compounds, the mechanisms and laws of the chemical reaction process in a school chemistry course, it is appropriate to use various models and methods of modeling chemical objects and phenomena. In the conditions of informatization of education, the modeling method, which is based on the use of ICT in chemistry and is one of the most important and effective methods of learning, occupies a special place among the methods of teaching chemistry. However, despite the fact that schools are equipped with computers, the computer modeling method in chemistry teaching in modern schools is not used in practice due to the insufficient methodological training of teachers, and at the same time, the appropriate software and electronic tools have not been developed. S.G. In Tchaikov's scientific work, special attention was paid to the use of ICT in solving chemical problems. The author has developed the main criteria for collecting and selecting problems in chemistry to teach them to solve them with the help of a computer using simulators in an interactive manner. It should be noted that this is probably the only study on this issue.

Methodological literature on chemistry raises the issue of using multimedia in chemistry education. Theoretical foundations of media education and the use of educational video films in chemistry classes A.A. Jurina. Dissertation research A.A. Jurina is dedicated to developing ways and means of integrating media education with the school chemistry course. Analyzing the means of teaching chemistry and integral medical education, A.A. Zhurin pays special attention to on-screen and on-screen audio tutorials created on the basis of video recordings of an educational chemical experiment filmed in a school chemistry class, as well as fragments of feature films and documentaries containing chemical information. In the training, the chemistry teacher, using the video presentation, first of all implements the principle of accuracy, because it will be possible to demonstrate experiments that

cannot be carried out in real conditions for various reasons (danger, difficulty of reactivation, duration). A.A. Features of the methodology of using educational video-presentation in chemistry teaching were developed by Jurin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the works of a number of authors, the problems of using the Internet in the process of teaching chemistry were studied (A.A. Jurin, A.A. Ragoyscha, etc.). It should be noted that the Internet is an important and very useful tool for working with educational information in chemistry. Today there is a whole complex of chemical sites. Many information technology centers in educational institutions, publishers of educational and popular literature create special educational sites and portals on the Internet. The volume of information resources is increasing, and there are some "guides" on the Internet that help the chemistry teacher. Ragoishi is addressed to chemists and is dedicated to searching chemical information on the Internet. However, the possibility of using chemical resources of the Internet in teaching chemistry and in methodical training of a chemistry teacher has not been specially studied.

Currently, within the framework of the implementation of the scientific-pedagogical program "Innovative Cluster Project" in 2021-2025, the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan is conducting the development of reference and information, control of electronic teaching-methodological complexes, diagnostic and interactive modules. These teaching-methodical complexes for the subject "Chemistry" are being created with our direct participation.

In particular, the electronic educational resource for the subject "Chemistry" contains the following: 1) information and information modules (collections of multimedia resources, educational databases, reference books and encyclopedic publications, manuals applications); 2) control and diagnostic modules (training simulators and test task management systems); 3) interactive modules (interactive

computer models of substances and chemical processes, virtual chemical laboratories, didactic computer games).

Resolution 213 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 14, 2021 envisages wide implementation of the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute as an innovative cluster of pedagogical education until 2025. Today, special attention is being paid to the problem of using the latest information technologies and distance education as a basis for improving the forms of pedagogical education in our Republic.

CONCLUSION

Thus, today, all the indicated directions of informatization of school chemistry education are being actively developed. However, the problem of methodical training of the future chemistry teacher for such work has not been studied until now. All this led to the need to develop a methodological training system and theoretical justification of the future chemistry teacher to work in the conditions of informatization of school chemistry education.

REFERENCES

REFERENCES:

1. Toychievich X. I. CAUSES OF HYPODYNAMY-THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN FIGHTING AGAINST IT //YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 27-31.
2. To'ychievich X. I. ATHLETES OF SURKHANDARYO ARE IN THE UZBEKISTAN PARALYMPIC TEAM TEAM. – 2022.
3. Ayubjon o'g'li, Azamjon Aliyev. "LOYIXALARNI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA AXBOROT XAVFSIZLIGIDA RISKLARNI TAHLILI." *Results of national scientific research* 1.4 (2022): 39-44.

4. Ayubjon o'g'li, A. A. (2022). LOYIXALARNI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA AXBOROT XAVFSIZLIGIDA RISKLARNI TAHLILI. *Results of national scientific research*, 1(4), 39-44.

5. Алиев, А., & Мусаева, М. З. К. (2021). СИСТЕМЫ ЗАЩИТЫ БИОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(4), 393-396.

6. Исмоилов, Ш. М., Абдужалилов, С., & Алиев, А. (2022). КЎНДАЛАНГ КЕСИМИ ИХТИЁРИЙ БЎЛГАН СТЕРЖЕНЛАРНИНГ ГЕОМЕТРИК ВА МЕХАНИК ПАРАМЕТРЛАРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ АЛГОРИТМИ. *Results of National Scientific Research*, 1(4), 49-56.

7. Xasanov I. T., Sodiqova D. B. Specific ways to develop physical activity in preschool children //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2022. – Т. 24. – С. 20-25.